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Transforming Education
for Sustainable Futures

CALL TO ACTION

Education for
Sustainable Cities
and Communities

JULY 2023

THE CHALLENGE

Cities are growing exponentially, while rural areas are often neglected. Education for sustainable cities and communities needs to be prioritised.

Rapid urbanisation, rural neglect and inadequate infrastructure and basic services create challenges for communities.

As cities grow both spatially and demographically, formally semi-urban areas become urban. Rural areas experience depopulation and movement of people (especially youth) as cities grow.

In rapidly developing cities, urban dwellers experience enormous challenges including: lack of arable land, high cost of living, poor housing conditions, scarcity of water, food, waste management, and insufficient skills to adjust to urban life.

Some cities are also very unequal, and marginalised communities are left without adequate access to essential services such as water, sanitation and waste management, creating environmental health risks and human rights infringements.

Across the TESF Network, projects focussed on exploring how education and training can be transformed so that urban dwellers acquire skills, knowledge, and competences to mitigate urban challenges and develop sustainable cities and communities. Projects found that education in urban areas needs to include communities, politicians, planners, and community leaders. In rural areas, traditional leaders also need to be included. New forms of solidarity are needed.

WHAT NEEDS TO BE TAKEN SERIOUSLY

... evidence informed
recommendations for
transformative
education that **co-
creates sustainable
cities and communities**

Transformative knowledge needs to be co-created with, and co-owned by those impacted by the challenges of urban and rural living in changing conditions.

Findings from across the TESF Network projects show the power of co-creation as a design principle where all people, irrespective of the status, are involved in generating knowledge about their lives and in response to their challenges.

For example:

In **India**, a project on Reimagining the urban from the perspectives of the marginalised explored the relationship between education and the margins of the city. The study found that knowledges can be co-generated to make way for education that is transforming and empowering in nature.

In **Rwanda**, a project on Skills for sustainable urban futures supported communities to develop financial literacy and innovative Community Development projects.

In **South Africa**, projects supported urban communities to strengthen food and water security through practical projects and organised activism. In the **Horn of Africa**, a project focussed on Inclusion of the deaf in developing their capabilities for work.

All studies found that establishing relations of trust is central to knowledge co-creation and co-ownership.

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There is a need to explicitly nurture empathy and build trust in teaching and learning spaces

Trust and empathy is important in teaching/learning spaces that are developed in support of co-engaged sustainability co-construction in urban and rural communities.

TESF Network projects found that this principle is critical whether nurtured in shared spaces for co-designing sustainable cities and communities, or as explicitly embedded during the norms of engagement in a research practice.

For example:

In **South Africa**, in a woman-led project focussing on defending communities from mining extractivism, reference is made moments where they discovered the importance of being 'transparent' with participants, and the need to be explicit about the ethics of engagement.

In **India**, reference is made to the tendency to alternate between the two emotional states - compassionating and resisting while embracing teaching /learning experiences that are transformative:

“We learnt to communicate and empathise with the other person, even if our perspectives were not similar. We do not have to put ourselves and others on the cross. If your view opposes mine, you are not my enemy, I can listen to you”.

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Urban education should pro-actively engage problem solving and seeking out of alternatives, to sustainably mitigate the pressures of urban life. It should be relevant to people's lives.

The TESF Network projects that were working on the theme of sustainable cities and communities all recommend strategies to develop knowledge, skills, values and competences that help people to address those practical human issues and conditions faced by urban dwellers.

They argue that education needs to be relevant to the lives of people, and engage their matters of concern, to have a transformative impact, especially for the most vulnerable or marginalised in cities and communities.

Such education also needs to be integrated into the systems and structures that people are engaged with. Some of the TESF Network projects showed an integrated approach to city location, design and how educational institutions and programmes contribute to environmentally sustainable cities and communities.

A number of examples across the TESF Network + projects focussed on issues such as congestion, poverty, literacy (**Rwanda**) food security (**India**), Water Justice (**South Africa**), Eco-School for drought mitigation in **Somalia**, and poor housing. A project in South Africa also focussed on reclaiming identity and relations with the land through a decolonial lens.

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Democratise learning spaces and enable the use of indigenous languages in learning

Studies in the TEF Network project showed that using indigenous/local language and democratising spaces enhance the transformative power of education, ensuring mastery of skills for sustainable communities. Embracing local languages is important for meaning making, including in learning resources.

For example, projects in **South Africa** focussed on inclusion of local language and music cultures in food gardens, indigenous languages use in community demonstration gardens (**Rwanda**) and financial literacy booklets (**Rwanda**). An online indigenous language extracurricular course was developed in **Somalia**.

A water curriculum in **India** was co-created with urban water experts, grassroots organisations, educators, and scholars by challenging reductionist notions of thematic knowledge while showing how a meaningful interface can be built between practitioners, community-based organisations, higher education institutions and educators to touch on a key theme that relates to the everyday life of students.

In **Rwanda**, a Technical and Vocational Education and Training TVET school was transformed to incorporate a functional adult literacy class, Opening Schools for functional adults' literacy (**Rwanda**), and in **South Africa**, university students created more sustainable communities on campus.

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Use local resources and art forms as catalysts for dialogue on issues of inequality, responsible consumption and production and healing

Across the TESF Network projects, findings indicate that various forms of expression, including poetry, photography, illustrations, storytelling, have power for mobilising engagement in urban and other spaces of transformative learning. Using local resources was also found to be powerful in supporting transformative learning in urban and rural communities.

For example:

In **India**, cross-disciplinary systems thinking was used to engage students with the social dimensions of water and their relationship with questions of hierarchy, caste and water values. A water privilege game was created that helped students identify unequal access to water by different social groups in society and explore 'water-actions' to facilitate more equitable access.

In **South Africa**, a project capturing the 'geostories' of Citizen Science projects expressed: "Breaking isolation and silence requires the creation of safe spaces that accommodate diverse forms of expression (story circles, visual art, creative verse, mapping, Prezi etc.)".

In **Rwanda**, students felt safe communicating and GBV messages through drama, and in **South Africa** photography was used as a cultural expression on relations with the land. Art helped an urban community to heal their differences.

CALL TO ACTION

What we ALL need to do TOGETHER ...

EVERYONE has a role to play in co-creating education for sustainable futures for ALL in ways that advance sustainable cities and communities ...

What role are you [can you] playing?

Contribute to sustainable cities & communities through transformative education

A call to action

For Researchers: Involve city dwellers and rural communities, including vulnerable populations in early stages of research and action, including problem identification.

For Educators and Teachers: Acknowledge there are multiple ways of learning, and multiple spaces and locations other than conventional schools, colleges and universities. Appreciate that transformative learning cannot always be quantified by indicators like grades and explicit observation. Embrace lifelong education initiatives and non-conventional community education to empower vulnerable youth and adult city and rural area dwellers with skills, knowledge, values, and competences to live sustainable lives.

For Policy Actors: Ensure inclusive and participatory laws that govern cities and rural areas. Write laws and policy in languages that communities understand, including the most vulnerable. Make use of alternative education forms such as drama and other forms of art, especially for non-literate urban populations.

For Engaged Activists: Advocate for better urban life conditions by holding duty bearers to account for interventions aimed at improving standards of living and quality of life. Encourage rural and urban populations to participate in existing public education programmes, or create others where needed.

THANK YOU!!

visit: <https://tesf.network/>

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This CALL TO ACTION, compiled by Michael Tusiime with Amal Ali, Poonam Batra and Heila Lotz-Sisitka is based on the findings of 67 co-engaged research projects implemented across 4 countries in the Transforming Education for Sustainable Futures Network involving India, Rwanda, South Africa and Somalia/Somaliland. Overall co-ordination was supported by the University of Bristol and partners, with UKRI with GCRF funding. It was complemented by substantive in-kind support and collegial relations that contributed significantly to the project's outcomes and success through intellectual, social, economic, ethical and other contributions.

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